

Project ELIXIRxNextGenIT
“ELIXIR x NextGenerationIT: consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure for Omics Data and Bioinformatics”
Area ESFRI “Health and Food”, finanziato da European Commission – NextGenerationEU
Codice N° IR0000010

ANNEX 3 - SERVICE ACCESS PROPOSAL

Proposal filling

Research proposals must be submitted in English. Abbreviations should be explained. The proposal should include:

- Project Title.
- Researchers and research institutions involved (general information and contacts)
- Abstract (max 300 words)
- Description and purpose of the project including Title, Innovation, Approach, Aims, preliminary data in support of the proposed experiments, experimental design and anticipated results (max 1000 words)
- Requested service(s), as described in Annex I of this call
- Nature and number of samples to be analysed and any technical information.